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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies: Definition and Guidelines

- Preliminary TAIS, April 2020 -

Deliverable D5.2

Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants

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D5.2. TAIS preliminary guidelines [April 2020]

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About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
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<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author.

The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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RAISD Glossary

ARU	Action Research Unit
EC	European Commission
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
LGTBIQ	Lesbian, Gay, Transgender, Bisexual, Intersex and Queer or Questioning
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PRSF	Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum
RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trial
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RSS	Refugee Support System
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Time-based
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The current document presents a comprehensive overview of the concept and implementation of the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) in each RAISD project country.

It synthesizes a large pool of ideas and plans, many of which are still in the phase of planning.

The preliminary guidelines contain all these plans, while the final version of the guidelines (D5.3) will contain the detailed analysis of the implemented TAIS pilots only.

Also, it presents an evaluation of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic to the implementation of the TAIS in the first semester of the timeline (April - September 2020).

In some cases, there are two TAIS ideas exposed because given the circumstances, it has been impossible for project partners to decide which one will be feasible.

All country-specific TAIS information includes the following details:¹

- Short description of TAIS idea
- Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS
- Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS
- Personalisation of TAIS for meeting individual needs
- Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds)
- Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation
- Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation
- Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS
- Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

Learn more about last TAIS developments at <https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/>

¹ Compiled by the respective consortium partner institutions, April 2020: Finland - UH, Hungary - Menedék, Italy - CESIE, Jordan - YU, Lebanon - LIU, Spain - UCM, Turkey - AU. All country chapters were revised by UCM (lead partner) and Menedék (Work Package 5 leader).

1. The concept of TAIS

1.1. Definition of TAIS

The acronym "TAIS" stands for "Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies". It means implementing innovative, tailored and personalized services designed to respond to the specific needs of one of the vulnerable groups detected after carrying out interviews with vulnerable individuals and working with stakeholders in the framework of the Action Research Units (ARU).

RAISD Grant Agreement Annex 1 - Part B, pp. 5-6. defines the concept of TAIS as follows: "The project hypothesis is that these **contextualised strategies** will constitute effective ways of dealing with the needs of VGs [vulnerable groups] in FDs [forced displacement situations]. A context will allow identifying whether a practice can be applied in it, and the metrics evaluating if that kind of practice and its results are valuable for the specific actors in that context. The result for this specific objective is therefore the TAISs."

1.2. Actors and timeframe

National teams (Finland, Hungary, Italy, Jordan, Lebanon, Spain, Turkey) **including consortium member partners and stakeholders** (organisations, specialists, activists, civil society, etc.) of the ARU **will develop the TAIS.**

The TAIS is open to the participation of all the stakeholders that have been working in the ARU together with the consortium members. The degree of involvement in the TAIS may vary, so the commitment is decided by each organization. Social innovation is a key concept for setting the outlines of stakeholder involvement.

The time assigned for TAIS is around 16 months, with 3 evaluation rounds every 4 months. In each round consortium members evaluate the evolution of the social intervention project and implement the necessary improvements according to the problems detected.

RAISD Grant Agreement Annex 1 - Part B, pp. 5-6. defines the implementation of TAIS as follows: "In the pilots, the ARUs will implement mainly **workshops** that include the simulation of TAIS with the stakeholders, and the elicitation of their feedback. These stakeholders must represent all the relevant societal actors, as the objective is to come up with sustainable, yet efficient solutions, where the systemic function goal is a balance between resilience and efficiency. The workshops will be at least one full day activities.

Before the pilots, the ARUs will carry out some preliminary empirical fieldwork to gather information to identify the VCs [vulnerability contexts] they face (SO1) and the attention and inclusion practices they use for them (SO2). In this everyday work, they will create the criteria (SO3) and the mapping (SO4), as tools to match VGs and their needs with suitable practices. When **the units implement the recommended practices** in the pilots, these will **provide feedback** to validate the previous results in terms of whether the criteria provided a real assessment of the actors' interests, the practices could be applied in the VC, and the results obtained were those expected. This experience will be used in the development and evaluation of the method."

1.3. Intervention ethics and methodological framework

Implementation of TAIS is based on the following ethical and methodological foundations²:

- Socio-Ecological Model,
- Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI),
- Action Research Strategy,
- SMART Criteria,
- Actor-Oriented Evaluation.

1.3.1. Socio-Ecological Model

TAIS is conceptualized having in mind the social and political "ecosystem" in which it takes place. Three levels of intervention are distinguished:

- Micro level: individual / interpersonal. Family and affective-emotional context.
- Meso level: institutional. Interactions with communities of origin, receiving communities during transit and at destination, contexts of groups and associations, etc.
- Macro level: policy / law. It is very unlikely that we can achieve results at the macro level during the project.

Macro level is the context to keep in mind all the time and recommendations can be written aimed at the macro level but TAIS should be implemented on the meso or micro level. If there is an obstacle found on the macro level, which makes a given TAIS proposal unfeasible, it should be modified to something feasible.

Meso level is for institutions and organisations, and includes entities such as: refugee reception facility, service centre (general for all citizens or refugee-specific facility) and community-based organization (migrant NGO, pro-migrant NGO, relief agency). The types of intervention or change can be in terms of material change (improvement of material environment), improved accessibility (information, opening hours, location, and language), procedural improvement (new or different services, methodologies) or changes in skills, attitudes and/or knowledge of staff.

Micro level is for individuals, including expert staff (service provider), migrants or refugee individuals already in a vulnerability context, migrants or refugee individuals in risk of becoming vulnerable. Here, the types of intervention or change can be in several forms, such as awareness raising and improvement of interpersonal and intercultural skills, prevention of critical situations, rehabilitation restorative interventions, self-help and peer support, or monitoring and improvement of work methodologies.

1.3.2. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Research needs must arise, first of all, from the social group. TAIS design is not started until the group for which the action research is being carried out is consulted.

² Elaborated jointly by UCM and Menedék.

A balance in terms of public vs. private sector, for-profit vs. non-profit sector, ethnicity, gender and local communities should be reached, or attempted.

Ethical issues should be respected throughout the project: gender equality, informed consent, accessibility, respect for diversity, etc.

1.3.3. Action Research Strategy

The anticipation and reflection of innovative action research should enable the TAIS participants to visualize their impact on society and reflect the underlying values and objectives of research in the short, medium and long term.

An action research perspective guarantees that the project is flexible, and that it can be adapted to the changes in the needs expressed by participants.

TAIS implementation should be inclusive, i.e. it should incorporate the opinions of the stakeholders and of the social group that participates in it; **as well as accessible**, i.e. all participants should access the planning and implementation process in all its phases.

The concept of vulnerability should be assessed for each TAIS, in line with RAISD's Work Package 4.

1.3.4. SMART Criteria

Effective implementation of innovative TAIS should be based on the following principles: specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, time-based (SMART).

- **Specific:** it should be very clear what the TAIS plans to achieve.
- **Measurable:** the change should be defined and properly measured via indicators.
- **Attainable:** micro and meso level targets should be set, in a proportionate manner (time and money inputs should bring sufficient outputs),
- **Relevant:** It should be related to vulnerability (conceptual relevance) and to existing needs based on the interviews and ARUs (empirical relevance)
- **Time-based:** A full project cycle should be planned, and the timeframe should be realistic/feasible.

1.3.5. Actor-Oriented Evaluation

TAIS evaluation³ is based on an actor-oriented definition of indicators.

The **indicators** for the TAIS are discussed in terms of the following categories:

- **Hierarchy:** input/output – outcome/result – impact. It is suggested that lower level indicators should be set (input/output).
- **Perspective:** process-oriented – result-oriented. It is suggested that result-oriented indicators should be given priority.

³ Elaborated jointly by UH and Menedék.

- **Evaluation:** baseline, interim, final. It is suggested that baseline and final are a must, interim indicators only if reasonable.

The exact evaluation criteria should be set up individually for each TAIS by its participants, in line with RAISD's Work Package 7.

1.4. General principles of TAIS design: from evidence to strategy

In line with **RAISD's D3.1. (Ethics Plan)**, compiled by Menedék, TAIS targeting Vulnerable Groups (VGs) of Forcibly Displaced People (FDP), as well as related institutions and societal actors, should be consistent with the strict ethical guidelines concerning sensitive data, such as gender, age, ethnicity, health, sexual lifestyle, political opinion, and religious or philosophical conviction (see also part 2.3.2. on Responsible Research and Innovation - RRI). Therefore, all evidence stemming from interviews, ARU meetings and other forms of respondent-driven information exchange, should be treated with **confidentiality**. This means that TAIS designs, while they rely on VG and ARU inputs, can only work with anonymized information.

In line with **RAISD D3.2 (Work methodology & Guidelines)**, compiled by UCM, TAIS design relies on the **identification of good practices**. The consortium has worked together in order to define previously existing good practices of inclusion and differentiated attention practices of vulnerable groups of forcibly displaced people in each country. The main points to consider were summarized in D3.2 (p. 47) as follows:

- "Identification of stakeholders that made an identification of the practice;
- Criteria actors or stakeholder are using to assess them as a "good practice";
- Name and leading organization (contact details provided);
- Target VG and type of host community;
- Application setting: context;
- Objectives;
- Length;
- Requirements/ accessibility issues;
- Performance procedures;
- Difficulties or constrains for its implementation;
- Results;
- Comments."

Information sources for identifying good practices included vulnerable people themselves (through interviews), stakeholders (within the ARU or outside it), and literature review.

Concerning the procedure of working with stakeholder inputs, each ARU discussed existing practices and provided actor-driven criteria to help to conceptualize good practices.

Actor-oriented criteria were defined by D3.2 (p. 48) as follows:

"RAISD is expected to gain a depth knowledge on What does good mean for the different stakeholders that take part in the project according to the quintuple helix.

Therefore, specific works must be developed within each ARU for the identification and discussion of practices:

- Discussing principles, standards, norms, values... What principles, standards, norms, values are named and identify by each type of stakeholder?
- What practices really meet what VGs' needs?
- What and where are the differences?
- What are the common features?"

Criteria compiled though desktop research were also considered. D3.2 (pp. 53-56) lists a total of 28 sources that include examples or criteria of good practices, related to EU institutions, previous EU-funded projects, national or local initiatives. These sources include the Assembly of European Regions, the European Asylum Support Office (EASO), European Migration Network, European Web Site on Integration (EWSI), and a wide range of project documentation material.

Good practices were collected in D5.1. (Preliminary catalogue of good attention and inclusion practices), compiled by LIU. This document also contains a cross-analysis of the national contexts in each country where RAISD consortium members are located. Policies are screened for the following vulnerable groups: children, unaccompanied children, people with disabilities, elderly women, pregnant women, single parents with minor children, LGBTQ groups, and language minorities; as well as concerning human trafficking, health and mental health issues, consequences of torture, rape and other gender violence, other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, and female genital mutilation. Not only the legal background, but the implementation of laws, regulations and policies is analysed, and informal care practices are considered as well. It is also stressed that not only individual (micro level) good practices exist, but the inter-institutional (meso level) network of service providers can also be a field of intervention.

In light of these national contexts, D5.1 collects the information provided by interviewees and ARU members in each country about existing good attention and inclusion strategies that could serve as a model for new practices that could possibly work in the given country context. **In the seven countries, a total of 65 good practices were collected and discussed by the respective ARUs.**

TAIS design then followed the **framework set by Menedék, in cooperation with UCM and UH** (the latter responsible for evaluation in WP7). A questionnaire was sent out to partners in February 2020 in order to orientate partners in their planning process. The questions were in line with the structure of the country chapters (2.1. - 2.7.) of the present document, namely:

- What kind of TAIS pilot would you like to implement in your country? (If there are various ideas, please give a summary of each in 7-8 sentences)
- What is the problem or vulnerability that this TAIS targets?
- Who would provide the TAIS pilot, and who would benefit from it?
- How could the TAIS be personalized to meet individual needs?
- How would you distribute the actions in time? (3 pilot rounds)
- What would be a "successful" outcome?
- How would you measure and evaluate its success?

- When and how would you gather the data or evidence necessary for the evaluation of the TAIS? (data sources, indicators, timing)
- Please give a tentative distribution (%) of the given TAIS's costs by budget line (staff %, travel %, other goods and services %)!
- Is your current budget well designed for the TAIS, or would a reallocation be necessary?
- What elements would be necessary to take into consideration regarding sustainability (after the project's end)?

The planning process included at least one ARU meeting in each country, where stakeholders could participate in defining the outlines of the TAIS ideas. Menedék, as WP5's leader, provided a continuous support to consortium members. The first ideas were summarized in a draft version of the present D5.2 document, by late March 2020, and comments were provided from UCM, Menedék and UNIMED (WP6 leader).

Nonetheless, **the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic caused a considerable backdrop** for the process of planning. Partners were forced to continue the work from home office, and ARU meetings had to be suspended or transferred (and adapted) to online platforms. All TAIS ideas had to be reconsidered in light of the public health situation and the implemented measures of social distancing. **The RAISD consortium decided**, in online meetings held on 3 and 9 April 2020, **to allow the application of substantial changes to the design of TAIS, in order to be more responsive to the effects of COVID-19.**

As of April 2020, there are still many uncertainties concerning the future development of the coronavirus. Therefore, **the TAIS descriptions listed below are to be understood as plans that are realistic only if the pandemic can be contained by the end of 2020.**

2. TAIS design and layout

TAIS plans elaborated by each national team are summarized in the following overview table.

Table 1. TAIS plans as of 30 April 2020.

<u>Finland</u>	<i>Helsinki University</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Young asylum seeker men are isolated in reception centres, little possibilities for socializing with local peers.
<i>TAIS description</i>	Multi-lingual online forum: online discussions with asylum seeking men and their Finnish peers.
<i>TAIS structure</i>	Helsinki University + Red Cross gather volunteers and moderate online sessions, focusing on language and social interaction.
<i>Timeline</i>	Implementation 1 (Apr-Jun 2020) + Feedback 1 Implementation 2 (Sep-Nov 2020) + Feedback 2 Implementation 3 (early 2021) + Feedback 3
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Individual feedback; Online ethnography -> Increased wellbeing and language skills, sense of belonging.
<u>Finland (ii)</u>	<i>Helsinki University</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Lack of childcare services for asylum seekers.
<i>TAIS description</i>	Development of already existing childcare services in reception centres.
<i>TAIS structure</i>	Helsinki University mediates between reception centre professionals and asylum seeking parents for improving childcare services.
<i>Timeline</i>	Implementation 1 (Apr-Jun 2020) + Feedback 1 Implementation 2 (Sep-Nov 2020) + Feedback 2 Implementation 3 (early 2021) + Feedback 3
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Individual feedback; Participant observation; Targeted interviews -> Increased wellbeing and trust in institutions.
<u>Hungary</u>	<i>Menedék</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Institutional context is weak / hostile, many times refugees feel 'lost' and there is no clear guidance for social workers about solving complex bureaucratic or livelihood issues.
<i>TAIS description</i>	Trajectory monitoring toolbox for social work with vulnerable refugees: case profiles, risk assessment and a list of institutions that can help.

<u>Hungary</u>	<i>Menedék</i>
<i>TAIS structure</i>	Menedék and partner organisations develop "case profiles" based on real life experience of refugees, and find solutions for "typical" problems that remain unnoticed by most service providers.
<i>Timeline</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Round 1 (May - September 2020): Individual competence development of social workers and service providers: Menedék's researchers and ARU members create a preliminary "toolbox" of vulnerability profiles. Round 2 (October 2020 - January 2021): Testing the trajectories in real-life situations, incorporating the work outlined in Round 1 in the daily operation of the participating organisations. Round 3 (February - July 2021): Building inter-institutional cooperation, a network of the organisations that can solve a case.
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Interviews, tests or focus groups before and after each round of implementation -> A dynamic and easy-to-use guideline of trajectories to follow in the institutional landscape for different vulnerability profiles. Increased wellbeing and better social integration of refugees.

<u>Italy</u>	<i>CESIE</i>
<i>Problem</i>	<p>Difficulties in Learning and Training Environments (LTE):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High number of NEET among FDP Low FDP female participation High levels of training dropouts among HVG Excessive strictness of the paths and hours of commitment Identifying FDP's learning needs requires responsive analysis
<i>TAIS description</i>	Aim of the "Digitalised Personal Pathways" Strategy is to increase HVG's decision-making capacity by employing the DASI Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface) for FDP trainees/learners to have direct influence over their learning path's contents and modalities according to individual needs/variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, logistics and time availability, etc.).
<i>TAIS structure</i>	<p>Mutual beneficiaries and providers are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forcibly Displaced Women that are living and are exposed to highly vulnerable situations (e.g. Human Trafficking Victims, HTV). FDP/HVG Relief, support and community centres; Training centres and providers; teachers and trainers; Quintuple Helix Stakeholders. the ARU first, later the TAIS Observatory.
<i>Timeline</i>	<u>ROUND 1</u> (online): May-Sept. 2020 [6 mth] Design and setup of DASI Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface).

<i>Italy</i>	<i>CESIE</i>
	<p><u>ROUND 2</u> (in-presence): Sept.-Dec. 2020 [3 mth] Coaching sessions to use DASI and define individual goals with support of mentor/tutor</p> <p><u>ROUND 3</u>: A. Jan.-Jun. 2021 (in-presence) [6 mth] Providing training modules as selected by HVG paxs (Round 2). B. Jul.-Sept. 2021 [3 mth] Evaluation of met criteria and assessment of success.</p>
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Data collection and follow up on learners' profiling and mapping, ultimately assess if through participants' individually tailored learning path/experiences it is possible to increase participation and satisfaction and decrease early dropouts while in training. Minimum quality Standards responding to targets' need and comprehensive of offering an opportunity, managing process, delivering service or supplying knowledge.

<i>Jordan</i>	<i>Yarmouk University</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Vulnerable Refugees who are not able to cope with difficult experiences and may not be more flexible even with a supportive family and community environment. PSS inside centre are not enough with local lack of reliable psychosocial support for vulnerable refugees by operational support unit (R-SOS)
<i>TAIS description</i>	Psychosocial Support unit for refugees: Psychosocial Support unit (R-SOS) in Refugees, displaced persons, and forced migration studies centre of Yarmouk University. Development PSS support, training and evaluation in S-SOS unit.
<i>TAIS structure</i>	Yarmouk University coordinates a face to face and online dialogue of the NGOs and UN agencies, aiming at psychosocial development and capacity building, as well as digitalization of training material.
<i>Timeline</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation 1 (May- July 2020). Outcome 1: Developing several area specific modules, eg. providing PSS services, refugee protection, education Implementation 2 (Sep – Nov 2020). Outcome 2: Developing key indicators Implementation 3 (early 2021) feedback
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Vulnerable Refugees feedback online and face-to-face PSS. Increased refugee wellbeing and satisfaction, acceptability, performance, and viability of the pilots.
<i>Jordan (II)</i>	
<i>Problem</i>	Obstacles for vulnerable refugees related to access higher education, a need to improve their skills and competences to find scholarship and find a education fund.

	<p>Many interviews in Jordan showed that many of vulnerable refugees' families and students have many problems that could include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · financial problems · misunder-standing of educational system in Jordan · misunder-standing of the importance of finishing higher degree · - No or few of information about the scholarships that support high degree education, how to apply, where and when
<i>TAIS description</i>	Refugee Higher Education Funds (RHEF): a set of workshops online to define the needs and (good) practices about higher education teaching policies, opportunities, scholarships, to support the effective integration of migrants through education
<i>TAIS structure</i>	<p>The main beneficiaries are vulnerable refugee students. Donors who will provide scholarships. Jordan educational organisations such as university, colleges of local society, vocational training schools and centres.</p> <p>Yarmouk University (YU) will collaborate with Jordan universities, national and international institutions donor, NGOs, ministry of higher education in Jordan, vocational training schools and centres.</p>
<i>Timeline</i>	<p>Round 1: April to September 2020</p> <p>Round 2: October to December 2020</p> <p>Round 3: January to May 2021</p>
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	<p>Education statistics (enrollment and graduation data), assessment of education contexts -> Young refugees receive scholarships and they are able to complete their studies in Jordan and work in the education sector.</p>

<u>Lebanon</u>	LIU Lebanese International University
<i>Problem</i>	An alarming health problem which is the massive withdrawal from camps among displaced refugees who are under-privileged to be well nurtured in facing the COVID-19 pandemic and those who face a post-traumatic stress disorder.
<i>TAIS description</i>	An online awareness campaign , called Health 4 SEAD "Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development". H 4 SEAD will gear to engage in COVID-19 awareness, prevention and treatment information campaigns through on line dissemination
<i>TAIS structure</i>	Lebanese International University organizes workshops, delivers the H-4 SEAD course, together with LIUHealth committee, monitors the implemetation and analyzes the feedback
<i>Timeline</i>	<p>Round 1: May - September 2020</p> <p>Round 2: October 2020 - January 2021</p> <p>Round 3: February - June 2021</p>

<u>Lebanon</u>	<i>LIU Lebanese International University</i>
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Interviewing participants before and after the implementation; Observing improvements in displaced people's attitude and behaviour during the lockdown through the survey .-> Empowerment of displaced people living in refugee camps through online 2-minute videos.

<u>Spain</u>	<i>UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Difficulties during transit for African women, a higher incidence of sexual violence. Difficulty of integration, situations of extreme violence, racism and language. Being a single mother can be an additional challenge.
<i>TAIS description</i>	Female asylum seekers of sub-Saharan origin participate in workshops about social integration, labour insertion, empowerment, psychological and skills training (including entrepreneurship)
<i>TAIS structure</i>	UCM coordinates the workshops but migrants themselves tell their experiences to other migrants. Active participation, no strong power relationships. Volunteer students from UCM could receive credit recognition for acting as facilitators.
<i>Timeline</i>	UCM is currently working in the online adaptation of pilot 1. An estimation could be starting in June. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First round: June 2020- November 2020. • Second round: December 2020- April 2021. • Third round: May 2021 –September 2021
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Methods of evaluation are to be defined -> Better social integration of African asylum seeking women.

<u>Spain (ii)</u>	<i>UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Transgender women asylum seekers need safer spaces in host societies because of transphobia and violence; difficulty of finding a job, need for recognition and respect for their identity. LGBT androcentric groups also exclude trans women
<i>TAIS description</i>	Transgender women asylum seekers form a group of multiplying agents for creating safe and supportive spaces. Mapping of LGBTIQ+ individuals who could join, and mapping the needs of the group, are followed by the consolidation of the support network and carry out a concrete initiative. The group creates its own rules, narrative, argumentation.
<i>TAIS structure</i>	UCM coordinates the constitution of the group (identity, accompaniment and self-defence) and its consolidation, by mapping the concrete needs, establishing the intervention objectives, setting it in motion. (For example: entrepreneurship program, self-defence and

<u>Spain</u>	<i>UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid</i>
	protection program, etc.). Recommendations are given for member organisations of the official attention and reception system.
<i>Timeline</i>	Finally, this option was not selected to be implemented.
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Methods of evaluation are to be defined -> The group in operation is the major result. Another result would be the systematization of the process to make a guide to replicate the process in other spaces

<u>Turkey</u>	<i>AU Anadolou University</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Turkish society does not understand properly the vulnerabilities and fragile conditions of forcibly displaced people, there is a growing hate towards them, an additional effort from the host communities would be needed for better inclusion of refugees.
<i>TAIS description</i>	Civil Society and Media Trainings. Various stakeholders are invited to 'awareness' trainings which combat disinformation, fake news and hate speech towards refugees. Interactive trainings are organized for media, industry, non-governmental organisations and other stakeholders.
<i>TAIS structure</i>	Anadolu University coordinates the involvement of non-governmental organisations, academicians, media workers, industry, and others. The trainings will be held for the civil society and media.
<i>Timeline</i>	Round 1: Jun-Aug 2020, followed by feedback during the end of the summer Round 2: Oct-Dec 2020 Round 3: early 2021
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Reflections and feedbacks from trainings -> Changing attitudes, changed conceptions and thinking about vulnerable groups.
<u>Turkey (ii)</u>	<i>AU Anadolou University</i>
<i>Problem</i>	Many refugees in Turkey are young women, for whom direct communication and involvement in host society is almost impossible. However, they actively use social media.
<i>TAIS description</i>	Development of online 'buddy' services for young refugee women. Mobile technologies are used, including social media and new media, such as YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram. Based on these platforms, a buddy (support system) will be developed online through social and new media, and involving volunteers from Turkish society.
<i>TAIS structure</i>	Anadolu University's students and non-governmental organization members receive training and then they will be voluntarily providing their buddy service online; but this will be also

<i>Turkey</i>	<i>AU Anadolou University</i>
	monitored to be calibrated for better coordination. If necessary, Anadolu University will provide additional trainings through assessments
<i>Timeline</i>	Round 1: Jun-Aug 2020, followed by feedback during the end of the summer Round 2: Oct-Dec 2020 Round 3: early 2021
<i>Evaluation methods_goals</i>	Feedback from participants, data from online platforms -> More involvement and interaction between Turkish and refugee youth

Country-specific information is displayed in the following country chapters.⁴

2.1. University of Helsinki, Finland

Diverging from the other partners, two TAIS will be implemented in Finland to follow the double strategy in which two groups susceptible to vulnerabilities are acknowledged: Young single men and parents of small children. Pilot 1 is adjusted to the needs of the men and pilot 2 to the needs of the parents. Both of the preselected TAIS can be implemented within the financial and time-based constraints of the project.

2.1.1. Short description of TAIS idea

Pilot 1: Multi-lingual online forum. As a part of the statutory language tuition in Finnish reception centres, a voluntary group of young asylum-seeking men are invited to join, together with Finnish-speaking voluntary young men, in an online thread to discuss the experiences of asylum seekers and everyday life in the Finnish society. The discussions will be moderated and, when necessary, translated from languages used by asylum seekers into Finnish. Online forum is a new experiment in the field of Finnish reception centres.

Pilot 2: Development of child-care services. One reception centre providing comparatively wide-ranging child-care services for small children will be observed. Throughout the developmental cycles, the services will be further improved. Each cycle will last approximately six weeks. As a result of the developmental cycles, a model for child-care services for reception centres will be established. Pilot 2 aims to develop already existing services, not to invent new ones.

2.1.2. Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS

Overall in Finland, asylum seekers are among the FDPs in most vulnerable position. Particularly those who arrived in Finland during 2015-2016 have been forced to live in uncertainty with marginal legal status and with restricted rights for several years.

Pilot 1 is primarily targeted to young single asylum seeking men who are rarely seen to be in a vulnerable position. However, these men miss the support of their families, are treated as adults in the asylum process and reception system and are susceptible to discrimination and labour market exploitation and lack targeted services. More specifically, young asylum-seeking men lack the opportunities to use and learn everyday language with Finnish-speaking peers. Most of the contacts they have with Finnish-speakers are elderly women since they tend to volunteer through NGOs. Particularly in smaller towns and rural areas there are few possibilities in contacting Finnish-speaking young people. Moreover, according to several asylum seeker interviews, the language tuition within the reception centres is not enough, takes place only in classrooms and is too repetitive due to constantly changing teachers and learners and the huge diversity of educational backgrounds different asylum seekers have.

⁴ Compiled by the respective consortium partner institutions: Finland - UH, Hungary - Menedék, Italy - CESIE, Jordan - YU, Lebanon - LIU, Spain - UCM, Turkey - AU. All country chapters were revised by UCM (lead partner) and Menedék (Work Package 5 leader).

Pilot 2 is primarily targeted to asylum-seeking parents with small children. Parents of small children, particularly single parents, suffer from lack of child-care services while trying to cope in highly stressful conditions. In most Finnish regions, asylum seeking families do not have the right to early childhood education in municipal day-care centres. Asylum seeking children are entitled to enter the Finnish education system in pre-school at the age of six. Moreover, the level of child-care services provided varies significantly between different reception centres and this has repercussions on both parental and child wellbeing. Lack of childcare services means that parents are not able to focus on their own wellbeing and settlement while their children are segregated from the early childhood education and from Finnish speaking peers.

2.1.3. Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS

Pilot 1 will be mostly provided by the RAISD-project researchers and Red Cross voluntary workers. Discussants in the online forum will be asylum seekers and voluntary young men. Discussions will be moderated and, if necessary, translated by researchers. The need for contributions from reception centre professionals is modest. The aim is to engage one or two reception centre teachers in the pilot. Their task would be, if necessary, to be there if asylum-seeking discussants need help in writing their posts or understanding others' writings. Beneficiaries of the piloted activities would be both asylum seekers and voluntaries participating in the forum. For asylum seekers, the pilot would promote language acquisition, provide first-hand and practical cultural and societal information and function as a platform enabling positive and equal interaction with Finnish-speaking peers. For the Finnish speaking voluntaries, the forum would provide first-hand knowledge on asylum seekers' backgrounds, position in Finnish society and the problems they face. Due to its experimental nature, there is an obvious danger that pilot 1 will not be integrated to the service repertoire of the Finnish reception centres. It is therefore necessary to inform potential participants about the temporary nature of the pilot. However, the pilot participants are able to continue their discussions after every pilot cycle (without moderation and translations) if they wish to do so.

Pilot 2 is something that is already provided by professionals in certain reception centres. In later phases of the pilot cycles, the service provision will be developed in co-operation with professionals, researchers and asylum seeking parents. The most essential contribution of RAISD researchers will be to function as a link between service providers (reception centre professionals) and end-users (asylum seeking parents). In most cases, they lack common language and collecting feedback from the latter is thus hampered. The main beneficiaries of the pilot will be asylum seeking parents and their children. For parents, childcare services enable to invest time in rest, studies, and promotion of well-being while peer company, structures activities and language acquisition is offered to the children.

2.1.4. Personalisation of TAIS for meeting individual needs

The pilots are adjusted to meet specific group-level needs. However, throughout pilot cycles, it is possible to consider more individual needs as well. Individual level feedback will be collected either through online platform or face-to-face discussions. This feedback will help to develop pilots to meet more specific needs.

2.1.5. Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds)

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the implementation of the pilots will be postponed. For now in Finland, restrictions prevent the implementation since contacts between reception centre professionals and asylum seekers are cut to a minimum, most of the services are not provided and visiting reception centres is forbidden. Currently, it is likely that

safety measures will not be eased before mid-May. Consequently, the plan is to have the first pilot rounds between June-August 2020. This would allow us to analyse the feedback during September and then start new rounds in October-December 2020. The final round would then be implemented in February-April 2021. If this type of delay is not possible, there are two further options: 1) To decrease the duration of each pilot cycle and 2) to have only two development cycles.

The actual functioning of pilot 1 is quite safe from some of the precautionary measures due to its online nature. However, the risk at the moment is that Red Cross and reception centres do not have the human resources to cooperate in the pilot. These resources are essential in recruiting the asylum seekers and Finnish-speaking volunteers in the group.

Pilot 2 requires more face-to-face activities and travelling. At the moment, it is uncertain when the reception centres are able to restart the provision of childcare services. Moreover, to be able to evaluate the activities implemented in pilot 2, there is a need to compile real life observation data and it cannot be replaced by any other method. Therefore, travelling and visiting the reception centres need to be allowed before implementing the pilot.

2.1.6. Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation

In a general level, in both pilots, successful outcomes are related to increased subjective wellbeing of asylum seekers. In pilot 1, the more specific outcomes would be increased competence in the Finnish language, increased knowledge on Finnish culture and society and strengthened feeling of belonging to Finnish society. As for pilot 2, the specific outcomes would be increased mental wellbeing of asylum seeking parents, increased trust toward reception services and professionals and, in the long run, promotion of children's and parents' Finnish language skills and competences in the context of the Finnish society.

2.1.7. Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation

The success of the pilots will be evaluated by both process and outcome criteria. Process criteria are highlighted in the first two pilot rounds and include mostly qualitative feedback on feasibility of the pilots. Both service providers and end-users will be asked how the pilots meet their needs and how they could be developed. In more technical terms, the process evaluation will include measures on adherence (end-users), acceptability (end-users) and viability (service providers) of the pilots. Outcome evaluation will be emphasised during the final round of the pilots (and after the pilots as a process have been fully developed). At this stage, follow-up data sets will be compiled to estimate the effect of the pilots in promoting the well-being of the participants. A specific sets of measures will be used to survey changes in mental wellbeing and knowledge on Finnish society and language.

2.1.8. Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS

During the first two pilot cycles, the data will be collected during the activities. In pilot 1, the online platform enables the data production on a daily basis in the form of 'online ethnography' and targeted queries. As for pilot 2, participant observation and targeted interviews (with parents and reception centre professionals) will be used as a method to acquire feedback data during the activities. In the final cycle, mostly quantitative outcome measures will be conducted by conducting baseline and follow-up surveys to acquire before and after measures.

2.1.9. Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

The pilot 1 is a completely new trial in the context of Finnish reception services and will be mostly implemented with external project resources. Therefore, there is an obvious risk of the pilot remaining one-off effort. To avoid the risk, a lot of emphasis will be put on training of reception centre professionals during and particularly after the pilot cycles. Implementing the pilot 1 requires relatively little project resources. Travelling is not needed while some (subcontracting) resources need to be allocated for research assistants to be able to translate the information leaflets, feedback, surveys and the actual discussions as well if necessary. However, no budget allocation is needed since there already is money left for these types of subcontracting services.

The pilot 2 is already an existing practice in some reception centres. However, there is a great variation in child-care service provision between different reception centres, and, to our knowledge, few written models for these services exist. Thus, as a result of the pilot cycles, a model for good practices in child-care services in the context of reception centres will be created. The modelling will help the coordinating authorities (The Finnish Migration Service and The Finnish Red Cross) and other local actors (reception centres) to implement quality child-care services in other settings as well. Implementing pilot 2 requires little project resources due to the fact that it is already included in the service provision of some reception centres. Some money needs to be invested in translating information leaflets and consent forms (for asylum seeking parents) and carrying out the empirical work during the pilot cycles. The latter include travelling costs, conducting interviews and translating them and translating surveys. At the moment, the estimation is that the expenses are quite modest and no budget re-allocations is needed.

2.2. Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants, Hungary

2.2.1. Short description of TAIS idea

Working title: Trajectory monitoring toolbox

The aim of the TAIS is to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures: social workers and service providers in Budapest should be informed about who, where and how would be able to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees.

A central piece of the TAIS is a "toolbox" for social workers and stakeholders that contains evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" as well as the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field, in order to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and to reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals.

The toolbox has the primary objective to recognize and assess a context of vulnerability. Also, institutions and organisations could improve their internal workflow, as well as inter-institutional cooperation, to make trajectories less demanding, and vulnerability reduction more effective.

Previous good practices identified by ARUs - such as the projects "Let's work together for integration" or "SOS Refugees" aimed at non-formal structure building, or the "Refugee Outreach" initiative and the "Youth and Women's club" reaching out for individuals and specific groups, in order to improve their access to services they need, are experiences to build upon.

2.2.2. Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS

In Hungary, the weakness of institutions and inter-institutional coordination in the social sphere, as well as the difficult access to many institutions and services have a negative effect on the vulnerability of the forcibly displaced, as it has been shown by many of the interviews. It is so because funding for such institutions is low, the political context is hostile, and the service providing structures are in a difficult situation. Therefore, many times the root of the problem is that a client with complex vulnerabilities could not receive support at the right place, in the right time. Many people fall out of the scope of supportive services, because complex problems cannot be tackled by one service provider alone. Also, in many cases the vulnerabilities or traumas are caused by the asylum system (or the lack thereof), as seen in the interviews detailing the horrors of the Balkan route or the shock of the Dublin procedure.

The interview analysis showed that "coping mechanisms" are related to a "supporting environment" of the individual, which in turn can be divided in two fields: organic and institutional. Those who can rely on an organic supporting environment overcome the traumas and integration difficulties easier than those who cannot. For the latter group, it is necessary to develop an institutional environment where actors engage in a non-formal, dynamic cooperation based on the organic structures of the host society, in order to improve the resilience of vulnerable individuals and groups.

2.2.3. Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS

The network's central agent is Menedék - the mission of the organization makes it a central actor in a possible network. ARU members representing other institutions or organisations can assess whether they can provide specific services.

The beneficiaries are clients (vulnerable individuals) of these institutions or organisations, and social workers or service providers working with them.

The emphasis placed on social workers is due to the fact that many times experienced social workers have a good understanding of procedures in the institutional landscape, but there is a high fluctuation in the field, and if a knowledgeable social worker leaves an organization or institution, their knowledge is lost. It is therefore crucial to make these informal connections transferrable. ARU members can help a lot in this respect.

2.2.4. Personalization of TAIS for meeting individual needs

The base and the principal field of application of this activity is individual social work with vulnerable refugees. However, every circle of the quintuple helix can benefit from profile and trajectory descriptions that contain the analysis of typical cases, a "vulnerability checklist" for clients and the intervention maps for vulnerability profiles. Also, on the service provider side it can be important to take into account the emotional burden on social workers. A personalized approach should be helpful for preventing "vicarisation" i.e. when emotional burden takes its toll on the social worker.

2.2.5. Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds)

Round 1 - online preparation (all activities developing online due to the pandemic situation, until September 2020): Focus on the individual competence development of social workers and service providers (their skills, knowledge, attitude etc.) Based on RAISD's results, researchers and ARU members create a preliminary "toolbox" of vulnerability profiles and the possible trajectories of these model cases towards an acceptable solution of the problem. Stakeholder involvement should be designed having in mind the effects of COVID-19 on them. Social workers and service providers undergo a needs/skills assessment and an online capacity building training. Based on their feedback, the toolbox is finalized.

Round 2: (October 2020 - January 2021): Focus on testing the trajectories in real-life situations and on enhancing organizational capacities for incorporating the work outlined in Round 1 in the daily operation of the given organisations. It should include the revision of internal protocols and job descriptions and the establishing an external supporting structure (coaching, on-the-job training).

Round 3: (February 2021 - July 2021): Focus on inter-institutional cooperation, information sharing, as well as on building a network of the organisations involved, through the ARU's work and case-by-case coordination. In the meantime, the content of the previous two rounds are being implemented and improved constantly until a final evaluation.

2.2.6. Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation

A dynamic and easy-to-use guideline of trajectories to follow in the institutional landscape for different vulnerability profiles. It can take the form of a booklet or a checklist, but it should not be too extensive. Neither the description of the actors nor the legal background is needed - rather, the logic of the interactions written in a transferable way. Besides this tangible tool, participants' competence should also be developed.

2.2.7. Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation

The tool should have the status its components described at the beginning of the pilot (benchmark value) and at the end (final value). In the meantime, the feedback of social workers, service providers and clients could be collected. A successful outcome would mean that the model is relevant and effective for helping intervention in individual cases.

2.2.8. Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS

The feedback of social workers via interviews or tests should be a central piece of evaluation, to be provided as a benchmark (during round 1), and as a result indicator (during rounds 2 and 3) of the developed toolbox. Also, the improved inter-institutional information exchange could be measured twice via a test or scale of knowledge.

2.2.9. Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

The self-interest of participating organisations should make them interested in being involved in the network even after the project's end. The bulk of the work is to produce guidelines about vulnerability profiles, case trajectories and a network of service providers. Sustaining the achievements is less costly: an improved structure and more skilled personnel should be the base of a no-cost model.

Concerning the implementation, it is expected that a budget reallocation from "travel" to "other goods and services" is necessary.

2.3. CESIE, Italy

2.3.1. Short description of TAIS idea

Methodological Framework

A. TAIS identification process

In January 2020 the work for the TAIS identification was launched⁵. The ARU and Advisory Board member were informed about the Research outcomes and findings developed under *D4.1 Vulnerability Profiling* and *D5.1 Preliminary catalogue of Good (attention and inclusion) Practices_Italy* > aspects, elements and criteria to be taken into consideration while planning the different TAIS ideas.

In the case of Italy, the ARU comes from the evolution of the unit created there in the former H2020 project FoTRRIS (grant 665906), which was focused on RRI. This unit, called Competence Cell, brought to RAISD is expertise in RRI and have been extended according to the needs of RAIS regarding theoretical background and profiles to work with FDP. In this case, this promotes the future sustainability of the ARU, as it will benefit from the activities for the former Competence Cell in this line.

- **Step 0. Brainstorming TAIS**

February 2020: Set up of four working groups led by CESIE's cooperation Units' representatives - while taking into consideration and consulting input and feedback as expressed by the [Thematic Committees established during Fieldwork \(WP3\)](#). [First inputs of the working groups [here](#)].

- **Step 1. Benchmarking TAIS**

March 2020: Each working group was requested to benchmark⁶ their TAIS proposal against the actor-oriented criteria identified under D5.1⁷, undergoing a quality check as tool to check if the proposal would satisfy HVG's needs.

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfvn5dDAvqQF2YqeCO0ojcJfP0yLeaEz5ojo2PF9otbFkNuQ/viewform?usp=sf_link

- **Step 2. Exploring TAIS**

March 2020: Working groups were requested to detail their proposal by filling in the "D5.2 preliminary draft and questions" as provided by WPL Menedék.

⁵ Please see: ARU: Competence Cell meeting presentation 24/01/2020

⁶ *Benchmarking is the voluntary process of self-evaluation and improvement by systematically analyse practices and foreseen outputs in order to discover strengths and weaknesses and learn to adapt and improve the organisational processes.*

⁷ Please see: D5.1 Preliminary catalogue of Good (attention and inclusion) Practices_Italy

B. TAIS selection process

Ultimately the “Digitalised Personal Pathways” _TAIS Strategy was selected and agreed to be tested, it includes concepts and elements of most of the submitted proposals by the different working groups. Given the limitation due to covid-19, the ARU agreed on an option that could offer and include knowledge resources and involve experts of all different thematic areas of interventions⁸ and in a long term to be exploited and sustained by the use of the tool of a wider variety of vulnerable target groups.

TAIS: “Digitalised Personal Pathways”

The aim of the TAIS_ “Digitalised Personal Pathways” Strategy (from now on, DPP) is to increase FDP’s decision-making capacity by employing the DASI Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface) for HVG trainees/learners to have direct influence over their learning path’s contents and modalities according to individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes in Italy, logistics and time availability, etc.) and be enabled in the creation of their own Action-Plan. Applying the DPP strategy it’s the participant to select the subject(s) and type of learning experiences to undertake.

The DPP approach will allow the ARU to collect data and follow up on learners’ profiling and mapping, ultimately assess if through participants’ individually tailored learning path/experiences it is possible to increase participation as well as satisfaction and decrease early dropouts while in training. Moreover, the ARU will be able to provide information to Stakeholders and inclusion actors on what are the most and least selected training contents, learning outcomes and delivery modes so as to better align with real HVG needs when designing future “Learning and Training Environment” programmes.

2.3.2. Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS

From a micro and meso-perspective problems in Learning and Training Environments (from now on LTE), as reported by Stakeholders in D5.1 potential Good Practices identification, include among others⁹:

GP1: Bringing Young Mothers Back to Education

[VG: Young mothers between 15 and 25 years old].

- Engagement of the target group was unpredictable. Due to the very nature of the target groups and the barriers they face it was very difficult to keep participants fully engaged for the entirety of the programme, high dropout was experienced. Also there needed to be a lot of additional services set up in order to support their involvement in the training activities which was not necessarily factored into the project at the beginning.
- BYMBE assumes the autonomy of the young mother seeking help and advice and view this person as a ‘self-expert’. HVG’s constructed identities can often be difficult to reconcile with those of learners or students.

⁸ Please see: RAISD [WP6 Annex IV CESIE Version 1](#) (ARU: Competence Cell establishment report).

⁹ Further details in *D5.1 Preliminary catalogue of Good (attention and inclusion) Practices_Italy*.

GP2: Socio-labour integration paths

[VG: Unaccompanied minors, unaccompanied asylum-seeking children and young migrants arrived in the country as unaccompanied minor.

- the excessive strictness of the paths and the weekly hours of commitment in the apprenticeship (especially in sectors such as bread-making and/or characterised by cycles, such as agriculture) resulted to be not very consistent with the reality of the daily work organisation; indeed, these aspects risk to affect negatively the youngsters' overall training;

GP3: Health centre for asylum seekers and refugees

[VG: Immigrants, Refugees, Asylum seekers, those who migrate due to the unusual situation, irregular migrants].

- The fact that users often have complete confidence in the experts' opinion leaves aside almost completely the active participation: in principle they will and shall adapt to the indications given to them. They do not have that critical attitude that they want to manage their own for example.

GP8: Social and entrepreneurial capacities of migrant women

[VG: Migrant or refugee women living in Palermo, from Senegal, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Morocco, Tunisia, Syria and Chile].

- Focus groups have underlined how identifying learning needs requires first of all a thorough analysis in order to understand what competences and skills the women already possess that can be useful to the purpose of an entrepreneurial venture. In fact, in many cases migrant women are unaware of the value of the skills they possess, as they do not regard them as marketable skills, e.g. cooking, braiding hair, sewing, etc. "Women, especially young ones, have so much positive energy that needs to be channelled!" Once identified the skills they already possess, they can experiment with new ones, depending on their entrepreneurial idea.

GP14: Social inclusion processes for unaccompanied migrant minors in the City of Palermo

[VG: Unaccompanied minors and forced migrant young adults].

- Having UAMs as the only target group, even if it seems to be the priority for their inclusion path and for the actions towards their autonomy, has proven to not be an effective method to encourage the inclusion as a means of creating an intercultural environment, through the involvement of young local people.
- Another challenge has been the involvement of unaccompanied minor girls; even considering that their number is significantly inferior compared to the boys, there are many obstacles to reach them and enable their participation. Despite the fact that UAMs feel the sense of belonging in the city, the lack of participation in the city sphere's activities, does not allow them to be known and interact with other aspects of the city, outside of those involved and who are more aware of the migration field.

GP16: Researching Female Genital Mutilation Intervention Programmes Linked to African Communities in the EU

[VG: HV Women and migrant communities that are still practicing Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) in Europe].

- Many participants often deserted the meetings at the last moment; others (especially women) were often shy and reticent about the topic.
- Initial resistance of participants to take part in the workshops because of the denial of facing delicate topics and speak about them openly.
- The lack of knowledge of Italian or English language created a barrier for answering the questions and made some participant feeling uncomfortable.

2.3.3. Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS

Mutual beneficiaries and providers:

1. Highly Vulnerable profiles among the Forcibly Displaced that are living or are at risk of social exclusion dynamics and contexts > Forcibly Displaced Women that are living and are exposed to highly vulnerable situations (e.g. Human Trafficking Victims, HTV).
2. Training centres and providers; teachers and trainers; Quintuple Helix Stakeholders; FDP relief, support and community centres;
3. ARU Action Research Unit

2.3.4. Personalization of TAIS for meeting individual needs

Meeting individual needs is at core of the DPP Strategy that adopts the novelty DASI Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface). To date, in most national and European Learning and Training Environments, it is common practices that target groups are pushed into a programme flow and imposed content as considered relevant and exploitable by the training providers and content designing stakeholders. This new Strategy, applying DASI, allows HVG to be the directors of the learning content according to interest and needs as they will be able to select among different areas/fields of knowledge - with possibility of intersecting categories [e.g. (i) self-awareness and empowerment, (ii) Health and well-being, (iii) social integration, (vi) labour insertion, (v) soft skills, (Vi) Italian socio-economic and cultural contexts].

2.3.5. Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds: total 18 months)

Table 3. (Preliminary) TAIS breakdown by Activities/Tasks, Timing and implementation mode.

Description	Activities and Tasks	Timing	Mode
ROUND 1. Design and setup of the DASI Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface) where participants/users can choose their selective courses they would like to	DASI (Content creation)	May - June 2020	Desk
	DASI technical ICT setup	May - July 2020	Online
	Video tutorial on how to use DASI	July - August 2020	Online
	Video tutorial subtitles (IT, EN, FR, AR)	August 2020	Desk
	Data Analysis I	June – Sept. 2020	Desk

Description	Activities and Tasks	Timing	Mode
attend (Round 3), selecting among different areas/fields of knowledge - with possibility of intersecting categories.	Mentors/Tutors identification (possibly of migratory background)	July – Sept. 2020	Presence + Online
	Trainers Hub establishment	July – Sept. 2020	Presence + Online
	Training I: HOW to use DASi with HVG	September 2020	Blended
ROUND 2. Coaching sessions to define individual goals with support of mentor/tutor. Beneficiaries get familiar with DASi and guided in the understanding of content and learning outcomes to be achieved, on how to select options that respond to their needs and draft their action-plan developed according to the individual needs.	Stakeholder involvement > Contact making and MoA > HVG relief, support centres/shelters	July to Sept. 2020	Presence + Online
	Adopting DASi: n. 20 PAX (TBD) Highly Vulnerable profiles among the Forcibly Displaced that are living or are at risk of social exclusion dynamics and contexts >	Sept. to Dec. 2020	Presence
	Training sessions organisation (HR/time/venue/materials)	Sept. to Dec. 2020	Presence + Online
	Data Analysis II	Nov. to Feb. 2021	Desk
ROUND 3. A. Delivering training modules as selected by HVG participants.	Training sessions delivery to HVG	Jan. to June 2021	Presence / Blended
	PAX evaluation > Data Analysis III (1)	Jan. to June 2021	Blended
	Mentors evaluation > Data Analysis III (1)	Jan. to June 2021	Blended
	Trainers evaluation > Data Analysis III (1)	January to June 2021	Blended
B. Evaluation of met criteria and assessment of success and performance indicators.	Data Analysis III (1)	May to Sept.2021	Desk
	Data Analysis III (2)	July to Sept. 2021	Desk
	*Training II: HOW and WHY to use DASi > to stakeholders	Sept. Oct. 2021	Presence
	TAIS Observatory creation	Sept.Oct. 2021	Blended
<i>Scientific publications</i>	<i>1 conference paper</i>	2021/2022	<i>Desk+ Online</i>
	<i>1 Journal Citation Reports (JCR) papers</i>		<i>Desk+ Online</i>

Description	Activities and Tasks	Timing	Mode
Conferences and workshops	<i>*provide information to Stakeholders and inclusion actors on what are the most and least selected training contents, learning outcomes and delivery modes in order to better align when designing future programmes.</i>		Presence
Project workshops	<i>1 workshops organised by the project and focused on its works with at least 20 participants each from outside the project</i>		Presence

2.3.6. Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation

As much as possible, quantitative and qualitative data will be collected to provide an unbiased picture of the DPP Strategy system achievements. To assess and verify if through participants' individually tailored learning path/experiences it is possible to increase participation and satisfaction and decrease early dropouts while in training we will compare the new data with those collected by the ARU from previous training experiences [Data Analysis I].

Table 5. (Preliminary) TAIS Data Analysis III (2). Defining Success of "Digitalised Personal Pathways" Strategy

Comparing Performance Indicators			
INDUCED approach		SELECTIVE approach (DPP)	
Data Analysis I	Average (%)	Data Analysis III (1)	Average (%)
N. paxs [programme/training attendees]		N. paxs [programme/training attendees]	
N. paxs completing the programme		N. paxs completing the programme	
N. dropouts		N. dropouts	
Average length before dropout (in hours)		Average length before dropout (in hours)	
Level of satisfaction (1 to 10)		Level of satisfaction (1 to 10)	
Reasons for dropout		Reasons for dropout	
Training Length (in hours)		Training Length (in hours)	
Certificates issued (n.)		Certificates issued (n.)	
Other local stakeholders involved (n.)		Other local stakeholders involved (n.)	

The data gathering will then allow to:

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D5.2. TAIS preliminary guidelines [April 2020]

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- Set a common quality framework for Learning and Training Environments (LTE) tailored for any Highly Vulnerable target groups' profile, as identified in *D4.1 Vulnerability Profiling*.
- Enable quality assurance mechanisms and further improve learning and teaching environments for HVG.
- Evaluate critical points of the DPP approach implementation cycle.
- Support mutual trust, thus facilitating recognition and stakeholders' long-term cooperation, building a safe community around the highly vulnerable target groups along the inclusion process.
- Provide information to Stakeholders and inclusion actors (see 3.3.3.2) on what are the most and least selected training contents, learning outcomes and delivery modes in order to better align when designing future programmes.

2.3.7. Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation

Each participant selects/creates her own "Learning and Training Environment (LTE) = each pax has an individualised evaluation programme in relation to: DASI SECTIONS/CONTENTS chosen and the NEEDS satisfied (D5.1 Matrix).

2.3.8. Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS

The DASI Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface) allows the ARU to track users' profiling and mapping, Information and data gathering upon DASI registration will serve the Trainers-HUB to best organise sessions matching the individual learner profile, modalities and needs].

2.3.9. Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

The DPP Strategy and the DASI Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface) will continue operating after the end of the project as the ARU aims to increase the offers to select from, increment the number of users and diversify HVG profiles that can benefit from it. Given the flexible nature of the virtual organisation all thematic units are encouraged to use the tool with their own specific target groups.

The TAIS Observatory will allow for the discussion, sharing, multiplication and transferability of the innovative concept at regional and national level as DPP is expected to a) generate genuine and sustainable improvements in the Learning and Training Environments (formal and non-formal and b) improve the situation of Highly Vulnerable target groups regarding attainment, social inclusion and well-being.

DASI ensures sustainability as the tool is mostly implemented by ARU members' and being based on CESIE's server its updating and maintenance will not require additional funding resources at the end of RAISD's project lifetime. Moreover, the tool allows adopting and adapting knowledge resources that have been developed and approved within European project context in many years of activity. (See examples in Table 2).

Project resources as initially considered by the budget allocation should be sufficient for the set-up of the DASI Tool (Round 1) and Human Resources/Staff costs currently seem adequate for the implementation of the in-presence activities of Round 2 and Round 3 (Trainers and Data Analyst/Researchers).

[N.B. Details still to be defined].

2.4. Yarmouk University, Jordan

2.4.1. Short description of TAIS idea

Pilot 1: Psychosocial Support Forum. Since 2011, migration and forced displacement have led to a changing social life in the Jordan community where former residents and refugees with different backgrounds, personal histories and experiences live alongside one another. This situation has created fears, stress and pressure on vulnerable refugees and increased the level of instability and insecurity in Jordanian societies to the present day. Through forced displacement and refugee experience, traumatic experiences often get aggravated by the situation they face in refugee camps as well as in host communities, e.g. poverty, discrimination, violence, and hopelessness. Ongoing personal distress increases the risk of developing moderate to serious mental health problems over time (GIZ MHPSS Orientation Framework, 2017).

The well-being of individuals and of families from different backgrounds within one community highly depends on what they know about and how they support each other as well as their ability to cope with their personal situation. Most people are able to cope with difficult experiences and may become more resilient if a supportive family and community environment is available.

Psychosocial services and support structures significantly contribute to the well-being of individuals and prevent the need for medical support through non-clinical interventions. Psychosocial support can be described as "a process of facilitating resilience within individuals, families and communities. By respecting the independence, dignity and coping mechanisms of individuals and communities, psychosocial support promotes the restoration of social cohesion and infrastructure" (IFRC Reference Centre for Psychosocial Support, 2009).

The pilot covers distinct modules and combines interactive training methods, in-house seminars, e-learning and field activities/short-term internships. This approach of training at Yarmouk University and different NGOs will become increasingly better received by the trainers and refugees alike. Meanwhile, a pool of lecturers will be trained in interactive in-class teaching methods and e-learning, i.e. blended learning. Feedback sessions and training evaluations are used to increasingly fine-tune the contents and set-up of the training material in order to even better equip (potential future) psychosocial support service providers.

Pilot 2: We believe education is just as important for refugee youth as food and shelter. It is not just a basic right and necessity, but also a tool for recovery. Going back to school partially restores normalcy for young people and enables them to obtain knowledge and skills that will help them chart a successful career path and earn a sustainable income.

Working title: **Refugee Higher Education Funds (RHEF)**

RHEF TAIS will help vulnerable refugees finding the support to finish their higher education and training programs. Specifically, RHEF aims to:

- Help vulnerable refugee students to explore and understand the challenges and opportunities to access higher education.
- Help the vulnerable refugees' students to find financial help (scholarship) that support them to finish their higher education degrees (diploma, bachelors and master).

- Give a guidance for vulnerable refugees to choose the higher education program and degree in a way that can help them to involve in the society where they live.
- Help vulnerable refugees' students to make decisions about their education. By giving them a guidance to choose the university that could support him/her.
- Support students who are worrying about university work, friends, getting in trouble at university or feeling down.
- Give the vulnerable refugees recommendations about funded training programs, when, where and how to join it.

Stakeholder workshops will be conducted physical and online to define the needs and (good) practices about higher education teaching policies, opportunities, scholarships, etc. Based on the results, a blog will be created to support the implementation of RHEF TAIS.

2.4.2. Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS

Pilot 1: the well-being of individuals and families from different backgrounds within one community depends largely on what they know and how they support each other as well as their ability to deal with their personal situation. The primarily targeted is **vulnerable young men and women** who are rarely seen to be in a vulnerable position, who are not able to cope with difficult experiences and may not be more flexible even with a supportive family and community environment. Especially in northern Jordan as a rural area, there is little potential to support them. Moreover, according to many refugee interviews, PSS inside reception centres are not enough, they only occur in the classroom and are very frequent due to the constant change of trainers and the vast diversity of educational backgrounds of different refugees.

Pilot 2: Research shows that due to Jordan's financial difficulties, the government's attempts to revise clear and effective policies to accommodate for the influx of **refugee students** to the higher education sector are limited. So, there is a lot offers policy and program recommendations to decision- and policy-makers for the national and international communities and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), donors, education stakeholders and other institutions with the overall goal to improve and guide further practice and research in supporting displaced persons in protracted situations to access higher education and reap its future rewards. Jordan has several challenges are directly linked to the education sector:

- legal issues including lack of accreditation and citizenship alongside restrictive host country policies.
- inexperience in university application procedures or lack of academic and career guidance, which are potential pathways to the labour market or further education
- financial shortcomings. The demand for higher education continues to far outstrip the opportunities available in Jordan, thus creating a large pool of Syrian students whose socio-economic returns of tertiary education are limited.

In addition, in Jordan, there is weakness of institutions and inter-institutional coordination in the field of supporting refugee higher educations, as well as the difficulties for refugees to access and apply. Therefore, the main problem is that the students especially the ones with complex vulnerabilities could not have a knowledge to join higher degree

programs and training programs and how to get scholarships. Many interviews in Jordan showed that many of vulnerable refugees' families and students have many problems that could include the following:

- financial problems
- misunderstanding of educational system in Jordan
- misunderstanding of the importance of finishing higher degree
- No or few of information about the scholarships that support high degree education, how to apply, where and when.

The RHDF TAIS will be implemented to solve and overcome the above problems. It will help the vulnerable refugee students and their families to solve their problems. Also we will give chance for education higher degree scholarship providers to catch the right students who truly need helps and to provide their services in an official and organized way.

2.4.3. Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS

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2.4.4. Personalization of TAIS for meeting individual needs

Pilot 1: The pilot is adjusted to meet specific needs at the group level. However during pilot sessions, it is possible to consider more individual needs as well. Comments will be collected at the individual level either through the online platform or face-to-face discussions. These notes will help to develop pilot programs to meet more specific needs. Basically, professions can do direct calls to refugee students to check on their knowledge of understanding of basic support needed, also students can make online sessions, WhatsApp groups and Facebook messenger.

Pilot 2: The pilots are adjusted to meet specific needs at the group level. However, during pilot sessions, it is possible to consider more individual needs as well. Comments will be collected at the individual level either through the online platform or face-to-face discussions. These notes will help to develop pilot programs to meet more specific needs. Basically, professionals can do direct calls to refugee students and stakeholders to check on their knowledge about higher education, understanding of basic support needed, also students can make an online session, WhatsApp groups and Facebook messenger. This pilot can deal with their problems, help students learn new skills in a crisis situation such as getting on better with friends or controlling their anger, and work out ways to make it easier for students to adopt to the new situation.

2.4.5. Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds)

Pilot 1: The plan is to conduct the first round for both pilots between May and September 2020. This will allow us to analyse observations during the summer and then start new rounds in September and November 2020. Then the final round will be implemented in early 2021. (3-4 months/once a year (the length of the pilot will be adapted accordingly during the preparation of the training modules and coronavirus COVID-19).

Due to COVID-19 and lockdown in Jordan, we expected that the pilot will start in mid-May 2020.

Pilot 2:

- Round 1: April to September 2020
- Round 2: October to December 2020
- Round 3: January to May 2021

2.4.6. Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation

In general, successful outcomes are associated with an increase in the wellbeing of refugees.

In **Pilot 1**, the most specific results will be increased competency in PSS, the mental well-being of refugees, and confidence towards reception services and professionals. It also enhances the skills and competencies of refugees in the context of the growing knowledge of Jordanian society about sociology and promotes a sense of belonging to Jordanian society. The transition from face-to-face teaching to online delivery as a plan has a serious impact on assessments and evaluation. Although technology has been used earlier to support teaching and learning, the assessment aspect is often under-developed. Applying assessments online on those courses designed for face-to-face learning is a challenging task. Students, as well as faculty members, are uncertain about the procedure for administrating outstanding assignments, projects, and other continuous assessments.

In **Pilot 2**, general criteria are, to a great extent, in line with the so-called SMART criteria set. We can say we are succeeding if we achieve our goals and if we solve the vulnerable refugee students' problems and challenges. So, students being able to join the higher education and to complete their bachelor's degree in Jordanian universities by receiving financial support. In addition, to get improvement in the livelihoods of refugees by granting new legal work opportunities through improving the education sector.

Measuring the evaluation of this pilot would be most effective through adopting, with consent, using the following:

- Interviewing participants before and after the implementation of the project
- Assessing the student's emotional wellbeing and sense of stability before and after the program
- Quantitative and qualitative feedback from students through face-to-face and questionnaires. And then analysing available data, which could give hints to:
 - Recovering the strategy
 - Understanding the problems of refugee to be far away the educational system
 - Having a big picture about refugee education
- Education statistics- Statistical measurements (enrolment and graduation data), assessment of education contexts, receiving scholarships by refugee and their ability to complete studies in Jordan.

As discussed in RAISD project, TAIS evaluation is based on an actor-oriented definition of indicators. The indicators for the TAIS are discussed in terms of the following categories:

- Hierarchy: input/output – outcome/result – impact. It is suggested that lower level indicators should be set (input/output).
- Perspective: process-oriented – result-oriented. It is suggested that result-oriented indicators should be given priority.
- Evaluation: baseline, interim, final. It is suggested that baseline and final are a must, interim indicators only if reasonable.

2.4.7. Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation

Pilot 1: The pilot programs will be designed and managed in a culturally appropriate and gender-sensitive manner. Successful implementation will be from Yarmouk University. The reason for conducting an impact evaluation assessing the application and use of knowledge and skills acquired by the participants of the short-term pilot including results:

- The assessment aimed at gaining an insight into how far the knowledge and skills acquired in the training by the training participants to their working contexts and were being applied when interacting with their beneficiaries.
- To develop recommendations to the implementers of the training pilots in order to support the learning process so as to increase the impact of the courses on the quality of the participants' psychosocial support services or related activities.
- To develop an evaluation tool with the purpose of continuous use by the pilot coordinators at both university and NGOs for future impact evaluations.

The success of the pilots will be assessed through process criteria and results. Process criteria will be highlighted in the first two pilot rounds and often include qualitative comments on the viability of the pilot projects. Both service providers and beneficiaries will be asked how pilots meet their needs and how they can be developed. In more quantitative terms, the evaluation of the operation will include satisfaction, acceptability, performance, and viability of the pilots. Refugee students should receive regular information through emails and university intranets. Finally, the evaluation of results will be validated during the final round of pilot projects. During the run, follow-up datasets will be collected to assess the impact of the pilots on enhancing the participant's well-being. Specific sets of measures will be used to survey changes in mental health and knowledge of PSS.

2.4.8. Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS

2.4.9. Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

Pilot 1: The R-SOS unit of the Refugees, Displaced Persons and Forced Migration Studies Center of Yarmouk University provides academic, social, life skills and career support services to refugee students. It provides information on available free training topics that may be necessary to improve skills. Social activities and life skills training will be organized. Psychological support will also be provided to support refugees. Additionally, the R-SOS unit will be responsible for implementing community-based experimental psychosocial support. In order to do this, the following sustainability structure will be established: The R-SOS unit will be developed to train specialists at the reception centre during and after the pilot sessions in particular. Implementation requires relatively few project resources. There is need travel and subcontracting resources are required for research assistants to be able to collect, analyse, translate worksheets, comments, interviews, surveys, and actual discussions if necessary. However, there is need to allocate a budget for these services types.

Pilot 2: The general and basic methodology of this pilot is to work with professionals who works remotely for now from home till lockdown in Jordan is over, then these professionals might need after that to work from YU, the main idea is to set targets on this pilot to achieve on weekly basis. However, there is a significant difference in the provision of education services between different reception centres, and to our knowledge there is no written model for

education services in emergency situations. Consequently, as a result of the pilot courses, a good practice model for education services in emergencies will be created in the context of reception centres. Modelling will help coordinate local actors to implement high-quality emergency educational services elsewhere as well. Implementation of Pilot Project 2 requires project resources because it is already included in providing service to some reception centres. Some money should be invested in translating information brochures and approval forms and doing pilot work during trial sessions. The latter include travel costs, interviews, translation and translation of surveys. For the time being, the estimate is that the expenditures are very modest and there is no need to reallocate the budget.

2.5. Lebanese International University, Lebanon

2.5.1. Short description of TAIS idea

Given the current circumstances of the pandemic of COVID-19, LIU will adapt its TAIS ideas and mitigate its actions to meet the current needs of vulnerable people. LIU will undertake three pilot studies/ stages with pre, through and post based on the stakeholder's outcomes. Actually, stakeholders include, but not limited to, LIU Health Committee, Policy makers, Research community, Education community, Business and Industry, Society organization. The following steps will be conducted:

1. Collaboratively invite and work with LIUHealth committee as an independent consortium
2. Invitation of LIUHealth committee (Google meet /Zoom meeting on April 12)
3. LIU invited LIUHealth committee of x members with Chair presiding. The LIUHealth committee participated in a full day hands-on activities of brainstorming concepts to promote strategies on COVID-19 awareness campaign. ARU Team with LIUHealth committee applied a tool for creating a shared understanding to prioritize the **top three VGs to be piloted** using the Diamond 9 technique during the workshop with groups of stakeholders.
4. Based on the meetings outcomes, three piloting phases will be delivered (dates will be determined later on):
 - Round 1: May - September 2020
 - Round 2: October 2020 - January 2021
 - Round 3: February - June 2021

The workshop will be conducted based on the following process:

Parallel to the meeting, LIUhealth committee will deliver **an online awareness campaign**, called **Health 4 SEAD** "Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development". **H 4 SEAD** will gear to engage in COVID-19 awareness, prevention and treatment information campaigns through on line dissemination, but not limited to, community groups and religious leaders, telephone hotlines, flyers, posters, bulk SMS and WhatsApp messaging, radio announcements, focus group discussions, leaflets, billboards and mural drawings. broadcasted videos, brochures with instructions. The outcome of this pilot project aims at empowering a strong pool of NGOs and Information Focal Point networks all over Lebanon in preparing them to facilitate and support them to teach Syrian, Palestinian and displaced people in refugee camps through the LIU Health's active participation and sharing of practical experiences. The digital promotion topics will be broadcasted through a YouTube channel that include the following topics but not limited to: <http://www.liu.edu.lb/HealthCommitee.php>

1. Develop a QA forum through <http://www.liu.edu.lb/HealthCommiteeQA.php>

2. Orient displaced people with Post-war Stress Disorder Psychology in facing Corona and severe measures to limit the virus's infection rate by:
 - A. Supporting children (minors as secondary beneficiaries, not subjects of the research), pregnant women, elderly people, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immunocompromised
 - B. Having correct use of medical treatment for old, pregnant women and children
 - C. Improving sanitation awareness systems and health facilities.

2.5.2. Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS

The TAIS is geared at addressing an alarming health problem which is the massive withdrawal from camps among displaced refugees who are underprivileged to be well nurtured in facing this pandemic and those who face a post-traumatic stress disorder and points mentioned no 2.

The impact of the program will have an impact on the NGOs working closely with displaced people directly and even directly and indirectly with displace people in camps to enhance and deliver a holistic Corona Virus awareness camping to Children, pregnant women, elderly people, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immunocompromised. LIU Health committee will work to enrich all stakeholders with the coping tools needed to enhance them in developing their awareness and minimize the challenges in facing the COVID 19 pandemic trauma.

2.5.3. Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS

The Lebanese International University (LIU) is the ultimate service provider for the entire TAIS pilot through the LIUHealth Committee, government authorities, Information Focal Point networks and the NGOs on the inclusion of refugees, asylum-seekers and internally displaced people (IDPs) in national response plans. The top beneficiaries of this initiative are displaced people living in refugee camps and those who are underprivileged:

- a. food ration cuts due to underfunding
 - b. distance-learning and digital-learning programs,
 - c. hygiene chemicals
 - d. public awareness campaign underscoring the indiscriminate nature of the pandemic and the need to respond collectively
- In Round 1, LIUHealth committee will develop data collection system through online for all NGOs in Lebanon to help disseminate a survey
 - In Round 2, after developing videos and brochures, LIU will be addressing all the addressed problems mentioned in 3.5.3.
 - In Round 3, LIU Health committee will assess and evaluate the results of the implementation in pilot 2.

2.5.4. Personalization of TAIS for meeting individual needs

The TAIS could be personalized through enhancing the social, emotional, and academic intelligence skills among NGO partners with LIU and LIUHEALTH Committee so they can better respond to and manage the challenges in 2.5.3. Continuous feedback will be implemented to identify gaps.

2.5.5. Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds)

Based on the workshop outcomes, three piloting phases will be delivered (dates will be determined later on):

- Round 1: May - September 2020
- Round 2: October 2020 - January 2021
- Round 3: February - June 2021

2.5.6. Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation

LIU will implement work ethics, use SMART objectives as LIUHealth Committee continuous monitors the QA forum with daily responses by the experts on the committee.

Empowerment of displaced people living in refugee camps through online continuous 2-minute videos.

2.5.7. Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation

Measuring the evaluation of this pilot would be most effective through adopting, with consent, using the following toolkit:

- Interviewing participants before and after the implementation of the project (no minors);
- Observing improvements in displaced people's attitude and behaviour during the lockdown through the survey.

2.5.8. Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS

The data will be collected during the three phases:

- Before initiating the project
- Formative assessment (during the implementation of the project to identify improvement points)
- Summative assessment (at the end of the implementation of the project to assess the intended outcomes)

2.5.9. Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

- Results achieved consistently demonstrate growth and improvement over time
- Emphasis on cascading continuous professional development within the displaced communities on maintaining continues health stability.

2.6. UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain

2.6.1. Short description of TAIS idea

In the case of UCM ARU, headquartered in Madrid (Spain), we are experiencing an absolute impossibility to work with the target groups and holding face-to-face meetings due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

We have considered the option of remote meetings and consultations. However, the emergency work of the entities of the ARU, as well as the lack of technological resources and computer skills of vulnerable groups (that has been confirmed by UCM ARU entities), impede us from adopting online measures for the co-creation of UCM TAIS since the very beginning of the initial idea and throughout all the research and innovation process according to the principles of RRI.

Furthermore, any of the TAIS proposals cannot be conceived from a telematic approach, as TAIS themselves have the main goal of the active participation of the VGs, as well as giving an answer to the specific challenges and needs obtained from the fieldwork and the ARUs (empowerment and active role of VGs among the FDP). Due to COVID-19 crisis in Spain, even the representatives for the entities are not able to guarantee their participation in UCM TAIS at this moment.

Therefore, the only potential measure during this period of total uncertainty is postponing the implementation of the TAIS in UCM. Meanwhile, we can advance in the state of the art and on the adaptation of the methodological design to the TAIS.

With this decision we can respect the emergency work of the entities, and we will try to avoid a drastic change in RAISD methodology design and in the future impact of RAISD innovative results.

Due to the current emergency situation, during these weeks the information that UCM team has received from ARU members is scarce. **To advance in TAIS design, UCM ARU is working on the online adaptation of PILOT 1.**

Despite the fact that in the 5th workshop there was a representative of the VG of the second option, we need to obtain the opinion of more representatives of the VG to design a really relevant TAIS. Due to that, it is possible that, in addition to the 6th meeting of the ARU (online version), another meeting would be held only with a greater number of VG representatives to specify the design of the TAIS.

Before the focus groups activities of the TAIS, a summary of the recommendations obtained in the interviews of FDP were shared with the ARU:

- The difficulty in finding housing and stable work are the main concerns mentioned by all profiles of FDP.
- Labour orientation and access to internships. Concern for a true career and consider previous work or educational experience.
- Training in the host culture, not just the language (that should also improve).
- Training on FDP documentation for people who interact with the public: doctors, banks, police ... More empathy.
- Create a document that explains in a simple way and in several languages how to apply for asylum and what alternatives exist in case of denial.
- Lack of staff with adequate training.

- Training and public awareness about forced migration, such as the red card, what is an asylum seeker...
- Difficulty finding housing, especially in large and single-parent families.
- Develop an app that indicates what the red card is for.
- Relevant training adapted to the cultural level and needs of each person.
- Take care of the reception situation of especially vulnerable profiles when sharing a flat or room to avoid re-victimisation.
- The difficulty of adapting to meals, especially in the case of childhood.
- Activities that help integration with Spanish people.
- Nursery for parents who want to study or work. More necessary even in the case of single parents.
- In general, the interviewees would prefer to be better informed about their current situation and their alternatives if the asylum is denied.
- Increase study alternatives so that they are closer to the interests and needs of asylum seekers.
- Measures to alleviate the work stress of social workers.
- Greater importance of psychological care.
- More leisure alternatives for young people.
- Take greater care of the protection and anonymity of asylum seekers in the media.
- Start training as soon as possible to access the labour market.
- Address the nutritional needs of certain profiles, such as chronic illnesses.
- Provide information in multiple languages: inform people who do not speak Spanish and are completely unaware of what they are entitled to.
- Accelerate access to health care.
- Information to unaccompanied minors about the documentation request procedure. Also training and attention to facilitate the transition from minor under the Spanish system of tutelage to adults.
- Insist applicants on the importance of learning the language and training for employment.

We introduce the results of the 5th UCM ARU meeting held on February 25th 2020, with 3 asylum seekers, representatives of non-profit entities (ACCEM, Tayba Association of Young Muslims, Caritas, La Merced, Mundo en Movimiento and Red Cross), 2 researchers (from Complutense University of Madrid and Pontifical University of Comillas), a representative of the policy maker helix (Spanish Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration), as well as a representative of a non-profit organization specialized in social entrepreneurship (Ashoka) and a representative of a non-profit entity with some functions in the administration system (La Rueca).

The main objective of this workshop was to start the design of three TAIS proposals with three VGs among the FDP. With this aim, 3 focus groups were created.

Due to the great similarity of two proposals, these options are presented to the consortium as a single one that encompasses them. This idea was already mentioned by numerous attendants at the end of the workshop.

Therefore, we finally get two proposals of TAISs at UCM.

It is necessary to choose only one of them once viability, relevance and sustainability in the medium and long term are studied, as well as consider if they are measurable, specific and achievable in the times we have. Considering the COVID-19 crisis, we are currently working on an online adaptation of OPTION 1.

OPTION 1 Female asylum seekers of sub-Saharan origin. With or without children / family charges

Series of workshops in which social integration, labour insertion, empowerment, psychological perspective (for example, from art therapy) and skills training (including entrepreneurship) are mentioned.

These activities would be done from the social group itself, that is, it would also be the migrants themselves who form and tell their experiences to other migrants. Participants with an active role in the learning and exchange process, without strong power relationship. Try to exchange knowledge.

Another way to achieve social integration and reduce the necessary budget would be to have volunteer students from the UCM itself that could receive credit recognition in addition to a practical experience related to their education.

These activities would have as a secondary objective a change in the narratives of the migrants themselves, knowing that there are different possibilities, in the volunteers and in the university and in society in general, as this proposal and its results are disseminated.

Generate synergies among different entities, also with town halls and companies (internships).

Psychological support.

Someone must be the coordinator. In this regard it has not yet been discussed.

OPTION 2 Transgender women asylum seekers.

Development of a group of multiplying agents for SAFE AND SUPPORTIVE SPACES.

The first step would be to make a mapping identifying the key people. Mapping of the needs of the group, not only of the leader (expectations, and needs of the support network). Motivate participation.

In three months, consolidate the support network and carry out a concrete initiative.

The central objective would be the constitution of the group (identity, accompaniment and self-defence) and its consolidation, mapping the concrete need, establishing the intervention objective, setting it in motion. For example: entrepreneurship program, self-defence and protection program, intervention protocol on transphobia, support and self-defence strategies, recommendations for member organisations of the official attention and reception system ...

SUSTAINABILITY: It could be sustainable because the group can have continuity by itself. It is a constitution of a safe space in itself. It does not depend on professionals although it may require their support.

MEASURABILITY: A sufficient number of people is needed. That the group exists, is endowed with its own rules, narrative, argumentation. To respond with an action to any of the identified needs. Identity: by the support network itself is fulfilled. Dignity: safe space and identity would be fulfilled. The need for employability is less addressed.

LAUNCH OF THE TAIS: Groups of LGTBIQ + migrants. Contact them to find potential stakeholders.

The UCM would facilitate the infrastructure.

We have project leader. Referents (motor group).

Project presentation and information sessions.

Logistic support: UCM installation.

Firstly, the group should be equipped with a basic operating guide.

Secondly, group self-diagnosis and provision of operating standards have to be made.

The timing of meetings should be studied and flexible because there are people in the first or second phase in the asylum procedure.

One result would be the systematisation of the process to make a GUIDE to replicate the process in other spaces.

During the 5th ARU meeting, 3 other VGs were mentioned ('accompanied minors', 'unaccompanied minors under the system of tutelage' and 'former unaccompanied minors under the system of tutelage once that they become adults'. The first and second cases were dismissed because of the impossibility of working with minors due to the methodological and ethical requirements of RAISD project. In addition, in the second and third, statistics and experience of entities such as Raíces Foundation or the social group itself (represented by exMENAS Madrid), revealed that the percentage of 'unaccompanied minors under the system of tutelage' or former ones that seek asylum is virtually non-existent in Spain. Therefore, a TAIS with these VGs is not viable. Moreover, in the second and third case, the RAISD criterion of working within forced migration would not be fulfilled.

Regarding Option 1, the collaboration of the student community will be incorporated into the practical activities of different subjects at UCM. UCM RAISD team also participates in a teaching innovation project with lecturers from different Faculties at UCM that would ease this collaboration of the student community. Furthermore, these collaborative students will be rewarded for participating in these social intervention activities with free elective credits, as if they were taking a subject. So students will be interested in participating and having a commitment to the project. We recognise that the ideal option would be hiring a facilitator, but this is not a possible one due to the need for reducing expenses.

Regarding Option 2, we have followed the RRI principles of participation throughout all the process. Firstly, gender, sexual orientation and gender identity were factors of vulnerability that were obtained during the fieldwork (interview to experts and FDP, as well as during ARU meetings). Secondly, during the phase of design of the TAIS, this VG was again highlighted as a highly VG and selected by the ARU members to develop a TAIS proposal focused on their real needs. In fact, a transgender female asylum seeker, as well as entities that work with this social group and that have an expert knowledge about this issue, participated in our last ARU meeting helping to develop this Option 2. Additionally, before the focus groups activities of our last ARU meeting, a summary of the recommendations obtained in the interviews of FDP and of the previous results of ARU meetings (experts) were shared with the ARU participants.

2.6.2. Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS

OPTION 1 Female asylum seekers of sub-Saharan origin. With or without children / family charges

Greater difficulties during transit (migratory grief), which implies a higher incidence of sexual violence. Difficulty of integration at destination countries due to greater migratory grief, situations of extreme violence, racism and language. To these vulnerabilities, being single mothers or family charges can be added.

OPTION 2 Transgender women asylum seekers.

Need for safer spaces in host societies: the violence that is becoming more explicit towards trans women on the street. Great difficulty finding a job. Need for recognition and respect for their identity. Trans women victims of trafficking are also excluded. LGBT androcentric groups that exclude trans women.

2.6.3. Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS

In both cases, we have not yet discussed / decided the organizational model.

2.6.4. Personalization of TAIS for meeting individual needs

Not yet discussed / decided.

2.6.5. Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds)

First round: UCM is currently working in the online adaptation of pilot 1. We have not yet decided, an estimation for it could be starting in June.

- First round: June 2020- November 2020
- Second round: December 2020 – April 2021.
- Third round: May 2021 – September 2021.

2.6.6. Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation

Not yet discussed / decided.

2.6.7. Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation

Not yet discussed / decided.

2.6.8. Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS

After each round. We have to discuss about it to specify it more.

2.6.9. Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

Some examples were mentioned during the 5th ARU meeting. For example, in the case of option 2 as it is mentioned in question 3.6.1. However, regardless of the option that is finally chosen, sustainability of the TAIS must be discussed in greater depth.

A note on the budget: We have reallocated 4,000 € to the TAIS from travels, subsistence allowances, and advisory board.

2.7. Anadolou University, Turkey

2.7.1. Short description of TAIS idea

The Turkish RAISD team wishes to implement two pilots. As of April 2020, however, it is not possible to tell if both will be feasible, due to the uncertainties of the COVID-19 pandemic. A decision will be taken within a few months. If only one can be implemented, then Pilot 1 is preferred over Pilot 2.

Pilot 1: Civil Society and Media Trainings. In relation to various dimensions of the society (non-governmental organisations, industries, academia, media, refugee related organisations and other related) can be invited to 'awareness' trainings. Because there is so much misinformation, disinformation and fake news in addition to hate speech towards refugees. Especially, there are non-true claims from different levels of society stating that refugees receive huge amount of national and international aids besides some other privileges. Coming from these basic points, there is an apparent need for awareness trainings to reach different levels of society. These trainings can be done in the premises of media, industry, non-governmental organisations and others. These are interactive trainings so the participants can see their involvements and changes in their opinions. The ultimatum outcome of this pilot is to establish a group at the end, consisting of vulnerable group representatives and host community members selectively. Through the training, they will be learning and discussing about co-existing, inclusion and diversity, and representation in the society as stated above in brief. At the end and in relation to the trainings, these mixed groups will form a "rights monitoring group" within the city to see and report rights abuses of those vulnerable groups. This can be a very unique example for the country for the first time.

Pilot 2: Development of online 'buddy' services. When the refugees in Turkey are analysed, significant number of the refugees are women and young in age. Especially for women, direct communication and involvement in society is almost impossible. At the same time, women and young refugees do use mobile technologies. In addition, they are also active users of social media and new media, such as YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram. Coming from these characteristics, to answer the 'need to know' aspect of refugees, the buddy (support system) will be developed online through social and new media.

2.7.2. Problem or vulnerability targeted by the TAIS

In Turkey, refugees are among the FDPs in most vulnerable position. Particularly those who arrived in Turkey since 2011 have been forced to live in uncertainty with marginal legal and facto status and with restricted living conditions for several years.

Pilot 1 primarily aims to reach the host communities to make them understand the vulnerabilities and fragile conditions of forcibly displaced people (especially from Syria, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Iran, and other countries) from the region. There is a growing hate towards forcibly displaced people/refugees due to the new time segment. It is no longer the crisis period, rather it is integration. Accordingly, it truly requires additional effort from the host communities to understand the conditions and current life of forcibly displaced people. The target audience needs to understand the importance of diversity and inclusion as behalf of the ongoing integration period which includes almost more than four million.

Pilot 2 primarily aims to reach refugee women and refugee young people; and at the same time, essentially youth from the host communities. The buddy system is the first level to create support system from a distance and create an additional socialization process for both the refugee target audience and the host groups. According to numerous studies, forcibly displaced people live in their own communities and do not really exercise the possibilities of life, area, relations and others due their isolation. This will be an additional effort to create voluntary social service from host communities and also will serve for the wellbeing and co-existence of both sides. This can be also considered as needs-based approach.

2.7.3. Interaction of service providers and beneficiaries (including vulnerable groups) in TAIS

Pilot 1 will be covering almost various levels of civil society including non-governmental organisations, academicians, media workers, industry, and others. The trainings will be for the civil society and media but the true beneficiaries will be both sides, including host community members and refugees.

Pilot 2 will be covered by university students and non-governmental organization members. They will first receive training and then they will be voluntarily providing their buddy service online; but this will be also monitored to be calibrated for better coordination. Necessary additional trainings will be also given through assessments. During the COVID-19 period and during the effects of post COVID-19 period, those trainings can be tried to be done through online platforms; such as Zoom platforms. At the same time, all these truly depend on the technology capacity of individuals.

2.7.4. Personalization of TAIS for meeting individual needs

The pilots are adjusted to meet specific group-level needs. However, throughout pilot cycles, it is possible to consider more individual needs as well. Individual level feedback will be collected either through online platform or face-to-face discussions. This feedback will help to develop pilots to meet more specific needs. As both definitions indicate, we will benefit from rights-based approach and needs-based approaches according to those target audiences' reflections.

2.7.5. Distribution of the actions in time (3 pilot rounds)

The plan is to have the first round for both pilots between June-August 2020. This would allow us to analyse the feedback during the end of the summer and then start new rounds in October-December 2020. The final round would then be implemented in early 2021.

2.7.6. Defining "success" in the TAIS implementation

In a general level, in both pilots, feedbacks and reflections from all target groups will be crucial. In pilot 1, the more specific outcomes would be increased in terms of changing attitudes, but especially in ideas and thinking towards vulnerable groups. Their reflections and feedbacks from trainings will be instrumental. As for pilot 2, the specific outcomes would be increased through participating sides' numbers and their involvement and interaction. At the same time, the categories of needs addressed will be another criterion for success.

2.7.7. Measuring and evaluating the TAIS implementation

The success of the pilots will be evaluated by both process and outcome criteria. Process criteria are highlighted in the first two pilot rounds and include mostly qualitative feedback and reflections of the pilots. Especially, the second pilot will reflect through the way it becomes instrumental and functional and through the number of participants.

2.7.8. Data gathering for the evaluation of TAIS

During the first two pilot cycles, the data will be collected during the activities. The data will be gathered from reflections and feedbacks of the participants in the pilot 1. In pilot 2, the online platform enables the data production on a daily basis which reflects different levels of interaction.

2.7.9. Assessing the sustainability of TAIS

We need to transfer funds from other WPs for this TAIS step for pilot 1 and 2.

Due to COVID-19, arrangements in terms of TAIS include host community members (students, industry, media, non-governmental organisations and others), they are at this moment in great need to focus on their own situation (especially re-organizing things and maintain economy) and also vulnerable individuals. Simply, we are not priority for them at this moment under these alert conditions.

AU states that the TAIS cannot be guaranteed as AU TAIS is not a priority for stakeholders and future beneficiaries.

3. Conclusion

The current document presented a comprehensive overview of the concept and implementation of the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies in each RAISD project country.

As it was presented in the Executive summary and in the beginning of each country chapter, the document synthesizes a large pool of ideas and plans which were drafted in a participative process. Unfortunately, the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic to the implementation of the TAIS in the first semester of the timeline (March - September 2020) are still uncertain, and at this point it is not sure either, how the public health situation will be in late 2020 and early 2021 in the participating countries.

The preliminary guidelines therefore contain TAIS plans which were, to some extent, revisited in order to better fit to a changed reality. The implementation will take into account the steps of the original planning process, as well as the ethical and methodological standards of the project - however, it will have to be adapted to a different socio-ecological context than in which it was planned.

Nonetheless, the increased need for protecting vulnerable individuals in light of the COVID-19 pandemic makes these changes necessary, and the implementation of the project activities can be a very good way for directly assessing new challenges through coordinated action.

In this deliverable, the RAISD consortium has included all the pilots designed in the ARUs. We think that including this work is valuable because it is the result of collaborative work of all the stakeholders involved. In addition, because these practices can be the basis for their implementation in other organisations. Among all of the pilots, the ARUs have chosen those that will be finally implemented. The final version of the guidelines (D5.3) will contain the detailed analysis of the implemented TAIS pilots only.

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